

Thematic synthesis of DevSecOps definitions

21 Themes (Freq)	74 Codes [Papers contributed to the code]
Expansion to DevOps (4)	expansion to DevOps [S1-IEEE-08, S1-SC-21] (2)
	extension to DevOps [S1-SC-01] (1)
	extension of the DevOps [S1-GL-33] (1)
Dev, Sec & Ops (10)	development, operations and security teams [S1-IEEE-05, 08, 12, S1-SC-10, 21, S1-ACM-68, S1-GL-15, 19, 27] (9)
	dev/sec/ops [S1-IEEE-26] (1)
Culture (8)	culture [S1-ACM-45, S1-GL-10, 13, 26] (4)
	cultural approach [S1-IEEE-26] (1)
	cultural shift [S1-ACM-50, S1-GL-11] (2)
	shift the mindset [S1-IEEE-10] (1)
Collaboration (9)	collaboration/collaborate [S1-IEEE-08, 12, 26, S1-SC-10, 21, S1-ACM-45, 68, S1-GL-26] (8)
	team work [S1-GL-02] (1)
Breaking silos of security (4)	breaking silos of security [S1-IEEE-08, 24, 26] (3)
	break down the barrier [S1-IEEE-22] (1)
Sharing knowledge (3)	sharing that knowledge [S1-IEEE-08] (1)
	giving that knowledge to the different teams [S1-IEEE-24, 26] (2)
Shared responsibility (6)	shared responsibility [S1-GL-10, 33] (2)
	everyone's responsibility [S1-GL-10] (1)
	security is a part of everyone's job [S1-GL-12] (1)
	make everyone accountable for security [S1-GL-27] (1)
	at the top of every developer's mind [S1-GL-12] (1)
Philosophy (3)	philosophy [S1-GL-02, 19, 26] (3)
Communication (1)	communication [S1-GL-19] (1)
Combination of DevOps and SecOps (1)	combination of DevOps and SecOps [S1-GL-13]
Integration of security into DevOps (21)	incorporating security practices in the DevOps processes [S1-IEEE-08, S1-SC-21] (2)
	incorporation of security practices in a DevOps environment [S1-SC-10, 11] (2)
	IT processes with security approach [S1-ACM-04, S1-IEEE-21] (2)
	integration of security with development and operation [S1-SC-09] (1)
	integrating security principles [S1-IEEE-12] (1)
	integration of security processes and practices [S1-IEEE-10, S1-GL-10] (2)
	introduction of more security-oriented processes [S1-SC-22] (1)
	integrates continuous security into the original DevOps process [S1-IEEE-03] (1)
	injection of security principles and controls into the DevOps [S1-ACM-50] (1)
	integrating secure development best practices and methodologies into development and deployment processes [S1-IEEE-44] (1)
	integrating the software development and operation processes considering security and compliance requirements [S1-SC-11] (1)
	integrating security methods into a DevOps process [S1-GL-02] (1)
	integrating security practices within the DevOps process [S1-GL-26] (1)
	adding security components to each step of the DevOps [S1-GL-23] (1)
bake security into the rapid-release cycles [S1-GL-11] (1)	

	integrating security into a continuous integration, continuous delivery, and continuous deployment pipeline [S1-GL-16] (1)
	built-in security [S1-GL-04] (1)
Agile (4)	Agile [S1-ACM-45, S1-IEEE-03, S1-GL-05] (3)
	smart and lightweight approach [S1-SC-31] (1)
Security is the main concern throughout the SDLC (7)	security is the main emphasis [S1-SC-14] (1)
	security is given high priority throughout the SDLC [S1-ACM-07] (1)
	a key concern throughout all phases of the development lifecycle and even post deployment [S1-SC-31] (1)
	security practices are implemented at each stage of the cycle [S1-ACM-07] (1)
	security is implemented at the right level and at right time [S1-IEEE-24] (1)
	emphasizes the importance of sound information security practices [S1-GL-01] (1)
	adoption of security through the entire SDLC [S1-GL-19] (1)
Shifting security to the start (8)	puts security at the forefront of requirements [S1-IEEE-24] (1)
	shifting security to the early stages [S1-IEEE-06] (1)
	security from the start/beginning [S1-GL-04, 15, 33] (3)
	integrate security objectives as early as possible [S1-GL-10] (1)
	placing security practices early during the SDLC [S1-GL-05] (1)
	avoids any risk of security being an afterthought [S1-GL-01] (1)
Time reduction & Efficiency improvement (4)	time reduction [S1-ACM-04, S1-IEEE-21] (2)
	increase deployment rates [S1-IEEE-22] (1)
	shorten the SDLC [S1-GL-23] (1)
Security assurance (3)	maintaining a secure operational atmosphere [S1-IEEE-22] (1)
	identifying security vulnerabilities [S1-SC-31] (1)
	responsible for application security [S1-IEEE-05] (1)
Tooling (2)	reliance on operational tools [S1-ACM-45] (1)
	tooling [S1-GL-10] (1)
Automation (2)	automation/automating [S1-GL-04, 19] (2)
Security as code (1)	security as code [S1-GL-26] (1)
Quality (4)	without lost quality [S1-ACM-04, S1-IEEE-21] (2)
	quality affirmation [S1-SC-14] (1)
	high software quality [S1-GL-23] (1)
Authors of common definitions (19)	Mohan and Othmane [S1-IEEE_08, 26, S1-SC-09, 10, 11, 21, 22, S1-ACM-45, 68] (9)
	Rahman and Williams [S1-IEEE-08, 12, 44, S1-SC-22] (4)
	Carter [S1-IEEE-24, 26] (2)
	Carturan and Goya [S1-IEEE-21, S1-ACM-04] (2)
	Myrbakken and Colomo-Palacios [S1-IEEE-10] (1)
	Mohan, Othmane, and Kres [S1-SC-11] (1)

Thematic synthesis of DevSecOps challenges

30 Themes + 7 = 37 challenges	86 Codes. 73WL+53GL
C01-Cultural resistance and organizational opposition (7) *	developer resistance to integrate security protocol [S1-IEEE-08, S1-ACM-05]
	developers lose autonomy [S1-IEEE-06]
	resistance to change [S1-GL-15]
	challenge of the shifting role of security [S1-GL-37]
	organizational opposition [S1-GL-24]
	cultural resistance [S1-GL-20]
C02-Challenges of collaboration, communication and coordination (19) *	teams working towards conflicting objectives [S1-SC-08]
	insufficient monitoring of collaboration [S1-ACM-01]
	challenge of unrestricted collaboration [S1-IEEE-08, S1-ACM-05]
	coordination of security team and DevOps team [S1-IEEE-08, S1-ACM-05]
	un-trusted inputs causing isolation [S1-IEEE-08, S1-ACM-05]
	conflict between security and development [S1-IEEE-06]
	collaboration challenges [S1-GL-28, 29]
	conflicting aims [S1-GL-38, 40]
	failing to collaborate with the InfoSec team [S1-GL-18]
	lack of coordination between InfoSec team and developers [S1-GL-19]
	gaps between DevOps and Security teams [S1-GL-20]
	disconnect between security and development [S1-GL-39]
	friction between development and security [S1-GL-13]
	communication requirements [S1-GL-15]
C03-Neglecting security (3)	not prioritize security [S1-IEEE-06]
	focused on velocity, not security [S1-GL-17]
	neglect security [S1-GL-30]
C04-Lack of security awareness and responsibility (3) *	improving security awareness [S1-IEEE-06]
	nobody is responsible for security [S1-IEEE-06]
	security push-pull [S1-IEEE-06]
C05-Lack of security knowledge and skills, need for training (9) *	lacking security education [S1-IEEE-06]
	lacking knowledge and training [S1-IEEE-06]
	lack of security knowledge [S1-IEEE-08, S1-GL-38, 40]
	developers are not security specialists [S1-GL-15]
	being unfamiliar with common security risks [S1-GL-18]
	the skills gap [S1-GL-37]
	not enough company stakeholders are security savvy [S1-GL-39]
C06-Boundary between specialist & generalist (1)	the boundary between a specialist and generalist [S1-IEEE-06]
C07-Insufficient level of governance on DevSecOps adoption (1)	insufficient level of governance on DevSecOps adoption [S1-SC-08]
C08-Recruiting challenges (2)	recruiting challenges [S1-GL-24]
	understaffing InfoSec teams and engaging too late with the InfoSec team [S1-GL-18]
C09-Inconsistent security policies design (2)	inconsistent security policies design [S1-ACM-05, S1-IEEE-08]
C10-Challenges in decision level*	lack of clarity and transparency in strategy [Myrbakken and Colomo-Palacios' MLR]
	lack of commitment of leadership and senior management for DevSecOps adoption

	[Myrbakken and Colomo-Palacios' MLR]
C11-Lacking confidence*	low or no confidence in DevSecOps [Myrbakken and Colomo-Palacios' MLR]
	lack of trust and skepticism [Myrbakken and Colomo-Palacios' MLR]
C12-Difficulties in integrating security into DevOps without losing speed (8)	difficulties in integrating security practices into a fast moving DevOps pipeline without slowing down the process [S1-SC-08]
	implementing security in CI/CD [S1-GL-28]
	rapid pace of change [S1-GL-29]
	faster development process [S1-GL-28]
	keep up with the pace of DevOps [S1-GL-30]
	DevOps velocity [S1-GL-37]
	Slow security testing [S1-GL-38, 40]
C13-Difficulties in transforming to DevSecOps without affecting current process (1)	difficulties in running current product and services in parallel to its transformation to DevSecOps [S1-SC-08]
C14-Compliance requirements (5)	compliance requirements [S1-IEEE-07, 08, 11, S1-ACM-05, S1-GL-39]
C15-Neglecting change control in security (1)	neglecting change control in security [S1-IEEE-08]
C16-Lack of standards (2) *	lack of security standards [S1-IEEE-08]
	lack of tool standards [S1-IEEE-06]
C17-Ignoring processes and security essentials leading to technical and security debt (1)	ignoring processes and security essentials leading to technical debt and security debt [S1-SC-08]
C18-Lacking process and platform for communication, collaboration, and sharing information and feedback (1)	lack of common process and platform for communication, collaboration, and sharing information and feedback [S1-SC-08]
C19-Out-of-sync domains and cross team dependencies causing issues in adopting DevSecOps (1)	out-of-sync and conflicting domain specific bureaucratic processes for development, operation and security activities causing issues [S1-SC-08]
C20-Using unsuitable metrics (3)	using unsuitable metrics [S1-ACM-01, 05, S1-IEEE-08]
C21-Tradeoff between security measures and CI system performance (1)	the tradeoff between increased security measures, and the ability to access and modify the CI system as needed [S1-ACM-95]
C22-Interconnectedness of the DevOps process (1)	interconnectedness of the DevOps process [S1-GL-28]
C23-Continuous deployment chaos (1)	continuous deployment chaos [S1-GL-19]
C24-Poor visibility of security track record (1)	poor visibility of security track record [S1-GL-19]
C25-Inadequate privileged credentials and access controls causing cyber attacks (2)	inadequate controls provide an opening for attack [S1-GL-30]
	privileged credentials used in DevOps are targeted by cyber attackers [S1-GL-17]
C26-Lack of mature tools for automation and security (17) *	lack of automated testing tools [S1-IEEE-06, 08, S1-ACM-05]
	lack of integrated testing tools [S1-IEEE-08, S1-ACM-05]
	wrong automated deployment tools [S1-IEEE-12, S1-ACM-01]
	use of immature automated deployment tools [S1-IEEE-08, 12, S1-ACM-01, 05]
	Remaining manual security testing and need for automated testing performance measures [S1-IEEE-08, S1-ACM-05]
	inefficient Static AST tools [S1-GL-19]
	manual pen-testing becomes a bottleneck [S1-GL-19]
	mismatched tools [S1-GL-15]
	tool-centric approaches to secrets management create security gaps [S1-GL-17]
C27-Challenges of legacy system refactoring (4) *	challenging to automate legacy system [S1-IEEE-06]

	lack of cloud support [S1-GL-19]
	systems are not scalable [S1-GL-19]
	legacy infrastructure [S1-GL-24]
C28-Use of cloud and serverless computing brings security complications (21)	cloud security complications [S1-SC-25, 44, S1-IEEE-06, 16, 25, 39, S1-ACM- 19, 52, 59, 66, S1-GL-24, 29, 38, 40]
	attacks due to miss-configured cloud environments [S1-IEEE-33, 42]
	security smells in Infrastructure as Code [S1-ACM-06, S1-IEEE-28, S1-SC-26]
	serverless computing [S1-GL-28]
	cloud and open source environments lead to compromise of critical information, configuration errors, compliance issues and security breaches [S1-GL-20]
C29-Threat modeling scalability issue (2)	threat modeling scalability issue [S1-IEEE-08, S1-ACM-05]
C30-Containers and other tools come with their own risks	container and other tools can often be the reason for security concerns [S1-GL-20]
	workload containerization [S1-GL-29]
	tools come with their own risks [S1-GL-30]
C31-Complexity in managing different tools*	complexity in managing different tools [Myrbakken and Colomo-Palacios' MLR]
C32-Difficulty in simulating production*	difficulty in simulating production [Myrbakken and Colomo-Palacios' MLR]
C33-Availability and reliability of infrastructure resources, tools, automation, and network bandwidth for fast deployment cycle*	availability and reliability of infrastructure resources, tools, automation, and network bandwidth for shorter and frequent deployment cycle [Myrbakken and Colomo-Palacios' MLR]
C34-Challenges of cost control (2)	restructuring organization and implementing DevSecOps practices can lead to high cost such as salaries for security experts, costs on new tools [S1-IEEE-04]
	risk and cost battle [S1-IEEE-06]
C35-Conflicts between security and business (2)	security and business objectives are implemented using conflicting approaches [S1-ACM-64]
	dilemma in selection of business processes in product and service delivery for transformation to DevSecOps [S1-SC-08]
C36-Customer readiness for frequent releases*	customer readiness for applying frequent releases to production setup [Myrbakken and Colomo-Palacios' MLR]
C37-Difficulty in training users for using advanced tools*	users need to be properly trained when using advanced tools [Myrbakken and Colomo-Palacios' MLR]

Thematic synthesis of DevSecOps practices

64 Themes (38)	144 Codes (76) 219 WL+ 137 GL
P01-Cultural shift to security (2) *	cultural shift [S1-GL-41]
	change the security mindset [S1-GL-32]
P02-Improving collaboration, communication and cooperation (27) *	work collaboratively [S1-ACM-02]
	enhanced collaboration [S1-ACM-02]
	cross-departmental collaboration [S1-IEEE-04]
	collaborating development, operation and security [S1-IEEE-04, 12]
	close collaboration [S1-IEEE-12]
	collaboration within and between different teams [S1-IEEE-12]
	collaboration amongst different departments [S1-IEEE-12]
	collaboration between Dev and Ops [S1-IEEE-12]
	collaboration between Dev and Sec [S1-IEEE-12]
	collaboration between Sec and Ops [S1-IEEE-12]
	team collaboration [S1-IEEE-15]
	strong collaboration [S1-IEEE-15]
	strong communication [S1-IEEE-12]
	close communication [S1-ACM-02, S1-IEEE-09]
	communication of security requirements [S1-ACM-02]
	virtual communication [S1-ACM-02]
	face-to-face communication [S1-ACM-02]
	physical communication [S1-ACM-02]
	cross-functional collaboration [S1-GL-30]
	foster collaboration [S1-GL-25]
open contribution and collaboration [S1-GL-24]	
collaboration and integration [S1-GL-02]	
communicate and collaborate [S1-GL-32]	
improving empathy and cooperation [S1-GL-10]	
reducing friction [S1-GL-10]	
P03-Shared and collective responsibility for security (3) *	shared responsibility for security [S1-ACM-02]
	collective responsibility [S1-GL-02]
	assign security responsibility to one person from your DevOps team [S1-GL-28]
P04-Shared knowledge (3) *	knowledge sharing [S1-ACM-02]
	learn from each other [S1-GL-32]
	shared threat intelligence [S1-GL-24]
P05-Training, learning and education for security (6) *	training [S1-GL-06, 10, 32]
	cross-training [S1-GL-35]
	educate developers [S1-GL-25]
	security learning [S1-GL-14]
P06-Security champions (2) *	security champions [S1-ACM-02, S1-GL-10]
P07-Recruiting success (1) *	recruiting success [S1-GL-10]
P08- Continuous feedback loop (6) *	feedback loop [S1-ACM-15]
	continuous feedback loops [S1-GL-09, 13, 15, 22, 35]

P09-Make security a priority (1)*	make security a priority [SI-GL-32]
P10-Trust (7) *	trust [SI-ACM-02, SI-IEEE-29]
	trust worthy [SI-ACM-02]
	trusted relationships [SI-ACM-02]
	mutual trust [SI-ACM-02]
	implicit trust [SI-ACM-02]
	trust within the teams [SI-IEEE-29]
P11-Shameless retrospectives (1) *	shameless retrospectives [SI-IEEE-09]
P12-Commitment and agreement (1) *	commitment and agreement [SI-IEEE-29]
P13-Enhance transparency (2)*	transparency [SI-IEEE-29, SI-SC-09]
P14-Pragmatic implementation (1)	pragmatic implementation [SI-GL-02]
P15-Be reactive and responsive (1)	be reactive and responsive [SI-GL-32]
P16-Security policies (2)	impose policy and governance [SI-GL-41]
	implement security policies [SI-GL-30]
P17-Continuous improvement mindset*	continuous improvement mindset [Sánchez-Gordón and Colomo-Palacios' SLR]
P18-Leadership support*	Leadership support [Sánchez-Gordón and Colomo-Palacios' SLR]
P19-Shifting security to the left (early) (18)*	shifting security to the left [SI-IEEE-04, 24, 26, SI-SC-08, 11, SI-ACM-50, 81]
	moving security to the left [SI-GL-08, 09, 13, 15, 18, 31, 35, 36]
	integrate security during the planning phase [SI-GL-35]
	take a proactive approach to security [SI-GL-17]
	include security early [SI-GL-28]
P20-Security-by-Design (12)*	security by design [SI-SC-07, 08, 18, 20, 22, SI-IEEE-16, 29, 30, 36, SI-ACM-45, 69, SI-GL-31]
P21-Increase the visibility (2)	increase the visibility [SI-SC-09]
	enhance visibility [SI-GL-41]
P22-Good documentation, logging and reporting (3)	good documentation and logging [SI-IEEE-15]
	better reporting [SI-GL-02, 19]
P23-Compliance control (6)	compliance control [SI-IEEE-11, SI-SC-27, SI-GL-10, 24]
	identify compliance requirements beforehand [SI-GL-28]
	bridging the divide between compliance and development [SI-GL-02]
P24-Risk management (9)*	risk management (including risk assessment, risk treatment and risk control) [SI-SC-11, 18, 20, 22, 26, 40, 41, SI-ACM-03, SI-IEEE-34]
P25-Vulnerability and incident management (5)	vulnerability and incident management [SI-GL-14]
	Incident management [SI-GL-08, 10]
	vulnerability management [SI-GL-23, 30]
P26-Privilege management (3)	least privilege controls [SI-IEEE-33]
	privileged access management [SI-GL-30]
	secure access via secrets management [SI-GL-41]
P27-Software process maturity (2)	software process maturity [SI-SC-32]
	Building Security In Maturity Model (BSIMM) model [SI-ACM-01]
P28-MUSA security DevOps framework for multi-cloud applications (3)	MUSA DevOps framework for security assurance in multi-cloud applications [SI-IEEE-16, 40]
	MUSA Security DevOps framework (SI-ACM-52)

P29-Define security requirements (2)	define security requirements [SI-GL-06]
	security requirements and design [SI-GL-14]
P30- Define metrics (3)	define metrics [SI-GL-06, 19]
	measurement [SI-GL-02]
P31-Security review and evaluation (7)	security reviews [SI-GL-18]
	security evaluation [SI-GL-14]
	proactive security assessments [SI-GL-10]
	detect existing security flaws [SI-SC-09]
	make sure the basics of host and network security are in place [SI-SC-09]
	host hardening [SI-GL-10]
	application-level assessment [SI-GL-10]
P32-Version control, metadata, and orchestration (1)	version control, metadata, and orchestration [SI-GL-10]
P33-Common weaknesses enumeration (1)	common weaknesses enumeration [SI-GL-08]
P34-Operational controls validation and improvement (1)	operational controls validation and improvement [SI-GL-14]
P35-Keep credentials safe (1)	keep credentials safe [SI-GL-06]
P36-Automation (93)*	Automation [SI-ACM-01, 09, 49, 71, 72, 81, 95, SI-IEEE-06, 07, 09, 10, 12, 13, 15, 20, 21, 26, 38, 41, 54, 57, SI-SC-08, 09, 11, 17, 18, 20, 22, 26, 27, 32, 40, SI-GL-02, 04, 06]
	Automated/automating test/testing [SI-ACM-01, 09, 49, 81, 95, SI-IEEE- 06, 07, 09, 10, 12, 15, 21, 26, 38, 41, 54, 57, SI-SC-08, 09, 11, 17, 18, 22, 26, 27, SI-GL-08,11,13,15, 35]
	Automated monitoring [SI-ACM-01, 71, 72, 81, SI-IEEE-07, 12, 13, 15, 21, 26, 38, SI-SC-08, 09, 18, 20, 26, 40]
	automated/automating scans [SI-IEEE- 07, SI-SC-32]
	automated/automating code review [SI-IEEE-07, 12, SI-GL-23]
	automate as much as possible [SI-GL-25, 28]
	automate protection of business logic flaws [SI-GL-09]
	automate tools and security processes [SI-GL-17, 30]
	use automated security tools [SI-GL-41]
P37-Security-as-Code (5)*	Security-as-Code [SI-SC-08, 09, 18, SI-IEEE-06, SI-GL-32]
P38-Threat modeling (15) *	threat modeling/analysis [SI-IEEE-02, 04, 07, 11, 30, 36, 39, 61, 71, SI-SC-26, SI-GL-06, 10, 14, 25, 28]
P39-Continuous monitoring (22) *	Continuous monitoring [SI-IEEE-07, 12, 13, 15, 21, 26, 38, SI-SC-08, 09, 18, 20, 26, 40, SI-ACM-01, 15, 71, 72, 81, SI-GL-02, 06, 25, 31]
	24x7 proactive monitoring [SI-GL-24]
P40-Red team security drills (2) *	red team security drills [SI-IEEE-04]
	red and blue team exploit testing [SI-GL-24]
P41-Fault injection (chaos engineering) (1)	Fault injection (chaos engineering) [SI-IEEE-13]
P42-Container security (13) *	Container/Containerization security [SI-ACM-52, SI-IEEE-55, SI-GL-28, 41]
	run container as non-root users [SI-IEEE-55, SI-SC-09, 34]
	use the latest version of image [SI-SC-42]
	conduct deep scanning of container image [SI-IEEE-04]
	enhance security of Docker [SI-IEEE-31, SI-GL-10]
	security practices in Kubernetes [SI-IEEE-18, SI-GL-10]

P43-DAST (5)	Dynamic Application Security Testing (DAST) techniques integrated into a CI/CD pipeline [SI-IEEE-10]
	Dynamic Application Security Testing (DAST) (SI-GL-02, 08, 23, 25)
P44-RASP (4)	Runtime Application Self-Protection (RASP) [SI-SC-32, SI-GL-02, 08, 25]
P45-SAST (4)	Static Application Security Testing (SAST) [SI-GL-02, 08, 23, 25]
P46-IAST (4)	Interactive Application Security Testing (IAST) [SI-GL-02, 08, 19, 25]
P47-Combination of static and dynamic analytical methods (1)	a combination of static and dynamic analytical methods [SI-IEEE-15]
P48-Immutable-as-Code (1)	Immutable-as-code ensures the immutability of infrastructure and avoid accidental configuration drifts [SI-IEEE-33]
P49-Policy-as-Code (2)	Policy-as-Code is an attempt to code the policy itself [SI-IEEE-33, SI-GL-17]
P50-Design-as-Code (1)	Design-as-code: CAIRIS (Computer Aided Integration of Requirements and Information Security) model [SI-IEEE-36]
P51-Compliance-as-Code (1)	Compliance-as-Code [SI-GL-23]
P52-Adopting DevSecOps in microservices-based applications (8)	adopting DevSecOps in microservices-based applications [SI-IEEE-17, 43, 52, 57, 84, 86, SI-SC-15, 36]
P53-Advanced malware detection (1)	advanced malware detection employs machine learning and deep learning [SI-SC-32]
P54-Micro-segmentation (1)	micro-segmentation [SI-SC-38]
P55-Secure coding (6)	source code repository and scanning [SI-GL-10]
	secure coding [SI-GL-10, 14, 28]
	build preapproved code [SI-GL-18]
	conduct code dependency checks regularly [SI-GL-25]
P56-Sensitive information scan (1)	sensitive information scan [SI-GL-23]
P57-Software Composition Analysis (2)	software composition analysis [SI-GL-06, 23]
P58-Verify cloud infrastructure (1)	verify cloud infrastructure [SI-GL-28]
P59-Integrate security issues within your general bug tracker (1)	Integrate security issues within your general bug tracker [SI-GL-19]
P60-Configuration management (1)	configuration management [SI-GL-10]
P61-CI/CD for patching (1)	CI/CD for patching [SI-GL-10]
P62-Consumable security services with APIs (1)	Consumable security services with APIs [SI-GL-24]
P63-Separation of duties (2)	separation of duties [SI-GL-14, 17]
P64-Business-driven security (1)	business-driven security [SI-GL-24]
P65-Linear scalability and affordable cost (1)	linear scalability and affordable cost [SI-GL-19]
P66-Availability and business continuity management (1)	availability and business continuity management [SI-GL-14]

Thematic synthesis of DevSecOps metrics

16 Themes	20 Codes 7 WL + 13 GL
M01-Security-trained rate (1)	number of developers that have gone through security-training [S1-IEEE-06]
M20-Business metrics*	business metrics [Myrbakken and Colomo-Palacios' MLR]
	revenue [Myrbakken and Colomo-Palacios' MLR]
	key performance indicators [Myrbakken and Colomo-Palacios' MLR]
M02-Top vulnerability (3)*	number of mistakes in different security categories [S1-IEEE-06]
	OWASP top 10 [S1-IEEE-06]
	top vulnerability types and recurring bugs [S1-GL-43]
M03-Time spent correcting mistakes in each category (1)	time spent correcting mistakes in each category [S1-IEEE-06]
M04-Security review performance (3)	whether features undergo a security review [S1-GL-18]
	whether security review slows down the development cycle [S1-GL-18]
	how well security is integrated into the delivery lifecycle [S1-GL-18]
M05-SLA performance (1)	SLA performance [S1-GL-43]
M06-Critical risk profiling (1)*	critical risk profiling [S1-GL-43]
M07-Point of risk per device*	point of risk per device [Prates' MLR]
M08-Number of continuous delivery cycles per month*	number of continuous delivery cycles per month [Prates' MLR]
M09-Number of adversaries per application (1)*	number of adversaries per application [S1-GL-43]
M10-Adversary return rate (1)*	adversary return rate [S1-GL-43]
M11-Defect density (1)*	defect density [S1-GL-43]
M12-Defect burn rate (1)*	defect burn rate [S1-GL-43]
M13-Penetration test pass rate (1)	systems that are affected by internal and external penetration testing [S1-IEEE-06]
M14-Security test pass rate (1)	security test pass rate [S1-IEEE-57]
M15-Code scanning detection rate (1)	code scanning detection rate [S1-IEEE-57]
M16-Whether automated testing covers security requirements (1)	whether automated testing covers security requirements [S1-GL-18]
M17-Use of preapproved libraries, packages, tool chains, and processes (1)	use of preapproved libraries, packages, tool chains, and processes [S1-GL-18]
M18-Use of SAFe DevOps Health Radar (1)	SAFe DevOps Health Radar measures DevOps performance, by assessing the maturity of four aspects and 16 activities of the CI/CD pipeline [S1-GL-01]
M19-Number of issues during red teaming drills*	number of issues during red teaming drills [Prates' MLR]

Thematic synthesis of DevSecOps tools

16 Themes	56 Codes/Tools
Automation tools (11)	Chef [S1-IEEE-07, S1-SC-12, 20, 26], Jenkins [S1-SC-12], Ansible [S1-SC-20, S1-GL-04], Puppet [S1-SC-20], Gauntlt [S1-IEEE-06]*, SaltStack [S1-SC-01, 20]
Automated code review tools (4)	Veracode Greenlight [S1-SC-01], PMD [S1-GL-23], DevSkim [S1-GL-23], FindSecBugs [S1-GL-23]
Threat modeling tools (2)	IriusRisk [S1-SC-01], Microsoft threat modeling tool [S1-IEEE-39]
Containerization tools (22)	Docker [S1-SC-09, 18, 20, 29, 34, 42, 45, 48, S1-ACM-95, 99, S1-IEEE-31, 55, S1-GL-03, 10], Kubernetes [S1-ACM-52, 76, 89, S1-SC-20, 29, S1-IEEE-18, S1-GL-03, 10]
Container security tools (3)	Twistlock [S1-GL-42], Notary [S1-GL-42], Aqua Security [S1-GL-42]
Cloud security tools (7)	Terraform [S1-SC-12, 20, S1-IEEE-33], AppScan on Cloud [S1-GL-42], AWS Security service [S1-GL-42], ThreatModeler Cloud Edition [S1-GL-42], Trend Micro Cloud One [S1-GL-42]
Sensitive information scanning tools (3)	TruffleHog [S1-GL-23], GitSecrets [S1-GL-23], Talisman [S1-GL-23]
SAST tools (7)	Kiuwan [S1-SC-01], Flawfinder [S1-GL-23], Graudit [S1-GL-23], Bandit [S1-GL-23], Spotbugs [S1-GL-23], SonarQube [S1-GL-23, 42]
DAST tools (7)	OWASP ZAP [S1-GL-23]*, BDD Security [S1-GL-23], Arachini [S1-GL-23]*, Nikto [S1-GL-23], Radamsa [S1-GL-23], FuzzDB [S1-GL-23], Fortify Webinspect [S1-GL-42]
RAST tool (1)	Fortify Application Defender [S1-GL-42]
Advanced malware detection tool (1)	CodeAI [S1-SC-01]

Software composition analysis tools (3)	Retire.js [S1-GL-23], OSSAudit [S1-GL-23], OWASP Dependency-Check [S1-GL-23]
Compliance-as-code tools (3)	nspec [S1-GL-23], ServerSpec [S1-GL-23], OpenSCAP [S1-GL-23]
Vulnerability management tools (8)	Defect Dojo [S1-GL-23], ArcherySec [S1-GL-23], Snyk [S1-GL-10, 21], HackerOne [S1-GL-21], Clair [S1-GL-21], Stethoscope [S1-GL-21], Rapid7 Nexpose [S1-GL-21]
DevOps performance measuring tool (1)	SAFe DevOps Health Radar [S1-GL-01]
Monitoring and alerting tools (2)*	Suricata [S1-GL-21]
	NewRelic [S1-GL-42]*
	Nagios Icinga, Graphite, Ganglia, Cacti, Pager Duty, Sensu, Boundry, Pingdom [Mohan and Othmane's mapping study]
Cyber security tools*	Tripwire [Mohan and Othmane's mapping study]
	Snort [Mohan and Othmane's mapping study]
Logging tools*	PaperTrail, Logstash, Loggly, Splunk, SumoLogic [Mohan and Othmane's mapping study]